

Preliminary studies of a lysine-rich protein gene transferred into rice

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The nutritional quality of proteins in cereals such as rice, maize, wheat, and other crops is comparatively low because of a deficiency in some essential amino acids. Lysine is the first restrictive amino acid in these cereals. Lysine-rich proteins were isolated and purified from seeds of the winged bean (*Psophocarpus tetragonolobus*), a legume. According to N- and C-amino acid sequences of the protein, a pair of primers was synthesized from the deduced nucleotide sequences of both end amino acids. The lysine-rich protein cDNA was cloned by using the primers to run polymerase chain reaction (PCR) according to a cDNA template from a reverse transcription of mRNA of the plant. The purpose of this study was to transform lysine and the lysine-rich protein cDNA cloned from this legume into a japonica rice variety, ZH8, and study the possibility of improving the nutritional quality of rice by genetic engineering (Liu et al 1993, Sun et al 1998).

The plant expression plasmid pBRLys, which contains the lysine-rich protein gene (*Lys*), *gus* reporter gene, and plant selectable marker *hygromycin phosphotransferase* gene, was constructed (Fig. 1). The plasmid pBRLys carrying the *Lys* gene under the control of maize ubiquitin 1 promoter was introduced into immature rice embryos and embryogenic calli via a particle delivery system (PDS-1000/He). Transformants were selected using hygromycin and transgenic plants were con-

firmed by PCR, PCR-Southern blot, Southern hybridization (Fig. 2), RNA dot blotting, and *gus* histochemical assay.

Data analyses showed that lysine content in most of the 11 transgenic rice plants improved differentially. Three displayed notable qualitative improvement, increasing to 12.45%, 16.04%, and 9.10% (Fig. 3), respectively, compared with the lysine content of nontransformed rice plants.

Further genetic analyses of transgenic rice plants No. 2, No. 6, and No. 9 are still in progress. Simultaneously, the transforma-

tion of maize and wild barley is under way. Further research on the *Lys* gene would have great potential value for improvement of the protein quality of these cereals.

References

- Liu BO, Jing Y, Kuang TY. 1993. Screening of lysine-rich plant species and identification of the purified proteins. *Acta Bot. Sin.* 35(1):22-25.
Sun SSM, Xiong L, Jing Y, Liu BL. 1998. Lysine-rich protein from winged bean. U.S. Patent Application No. 08/964, 722.

Fig. 1. Plant expression plasmid pBRLys. LB = left border, RB = right border.

Fig. 2. Southern blot analysis of transgenic rice plants. Lane 1 = pBRLys/HindIII + KpnI as positive control, 2 = nontransformed rice plant PND/HindIII + KpnI as negative control, 3 and 4 = transgenic rice plant DNA/HindIII + KpnI.

Lysine content increment in the amount of amino acids (%)

Fig. 3. Lysine content analysis of transgenic rice plants. Notes: 1. Of amino acids in lysine-rich proteins, 15 were determined: aspartic acid, threonine, serine, glutamic acid, glycine, alanine, valine, methionine, isoleucine, leucine, tyrosine, phenylalanine, histidine, lysine, and arginine. 2. Each column represents the amount of lysine content in transgenic rice plants minus the amount from nontransgenic rice as a control.